

MUSEUM PEDAGOGY AS AN INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation: This article describes the history of museum pedagogy and its development, the educational activities of museums, as well as the cooperation of museums and educational institutions, as well as the functions of museum pedagogy.

Keywords: museum pedagogy, cooperation between museums and secondary schools, educational activities, methodology, innovative programs, functions of museum pedagogy.

In the process of independence, museums have become increasingly important in carrying out the tasks of educating the members of the society in the spirit of free, democratic thinking and national ideology. Museums and historical and architectural monuments of the Republic of Uzbekistan are a cultural awakening of the nation, to promote the national idea, to strengthen national pride and values in the minds of the people, plays an important role in strengthening the sense of commitment to the ideas of independence, democracy and confidence in development. Museums are not only a treasure trove of unique and diverse objects of nature and society, but also important links and centers of important scientific, educational and social communication.

Today, it is difficult to imagine educational or socio-cultural leisure activities without a museum component, as well as a qualified student and a qualified specialist who knows the specifics of museum work, especially the socio-cultural educational activities of the museum. It should be noted that this complex task is a

new pedagogical direction - in the framework of museum pedagogy, teaching and educating students on museum material, the formation of theoretical concepts in them, as well as the successful training of specialists who can solve pedagogical problems in the context of the museum environment and educational institutions. The new status of museums requires the development of various systems of training specialists for the implementation of the educational process in the museum educational environment, new forms and methods of cooperation between museums and secondary schools and universities.

At present, the relationship between children of different ages and museums and educational institutions is not focused on a specific goal. Museums are a social institution that combines cultural, historical, natural and scientific values in educating the younger generation in the spirit of respect for material and spiritual heritage. Therefore, a systematic and programmed approach to the activities of museums and schools in the field of education is required. [1;176]

Museum pedagogy is a discipline formed as a result of the interaction of pedagogy, psychology and museology. It is a field of science that studies the history and characteristics of museums' cultural and educational activities, the ways in which museums influence different categories of visitors, and their interactions with educational institutions. Originally, the concept of museum pedagogy was formed in Germany in the early twentieth century and introduced into scientific circulation. Its implementation is associated with the names of A. Lichtwark, A. Reichven and R. Freudental. Initially, the field was interpreted as part of the museum's work with teachers. In 1913, A. Lichtwark was the first to formulate the idea of the importance of the museum as an educational institution and proposed new ways of communicating with visitors. [2;230].

The German scientist R. Freudental was the first to create a method of teaching in the school system in museums, emphasizing the need for a pedagogical specialist to organize the educational process in the museum environment, and recommended

naming him "museum pedagogue."Freudental also outlined a number of requirements for teaching at the museum today:

- Each visit to the museum should be conducted as a lesson, with a clear purpose (educational, pedagogical, developmental);
- Teachers and children should know that visiting a museum is not just an excursion, but a serious business, and therefore it is necessary to prepare for it;
- It is advisable for children to visit the museum without getting tired and ready to understand;
- It is important to choose attractions, avoiding the general excursion, which is "difficult not only for the child's mind, but also for adults";
- The choice of exhibits for the tour should be based on the theme and the age and interests of the child;
- As a result of visiting the museum, it is important for children to create independent creative work (drawing, writing essays based on what they see, creating models, etc.).[3;29]

B.A. Stolyarov's search for new forms of interaction between the museum and visitors as a means of forming a valuable attitude to the educational activities of the museum, the historical reality, the world around us, issues of social and cultural activities of the population, the development of artistic perception, the formation of aesthetic education through the museum are analyzed in detail.[3;84].

The Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York, one of the largest museums in the United States, places great emphasis on educational purpose. It is known that the experience of German and English museums was used here to study and develop fine arts. Today, the width of the Metropolitan, quality of collections and excursions with visitors, events such as concerts, lectures, and film screenings show that the museum places great emphasis on forms of education.

The Metropolitan Museum of Art has published the first guide and teacher guide that will introduce visitors to the exhibits. Public lectures were given over the

weekend. A special "Metropolitan Bulletin" dedicated to museum education has been published, which includes a variety of programs for all categories of visitors, including lectures for the "general public," students, teachers, designers, and even the blind. However, despite the development of special programs for museum education, there is a significant difference between educational activities and museum education. That's why the Metropolitan Museum was one of the first to use historical objects, such as history, geography and showed the first example of how to conduct lessons in other school subjects using clothing, furniture samples, and other original historical objects.

Many foreign museums use theatrical performances. This is especially effective in museums of history and technology. These performances are performed by a group of museum staff in the form of heroes depicting a particular period, or by museum staff dressed in themed costumes. These scenes play an important role in engaging children and developing their historical thinking.

The challenges facing museum pedagogy today are multifaceted: visitors to feel the events on display in the museum, teaches listening, meditation, and learning. Creating conditions for the meeting and communication of different generations in the museum is important in understanding the essence of good and evil, wisdom and ignorance, truth and falsehood.

In the field of museum pedagogy, the museum's interaction with educational institutions is mainly considered. The reason for the popularity of this route is the large number of tourists visiting museums, using a variety of non-traditional teaching methods, to contribute to the study of the history of our country in the younger generation and their educational process.

In this case, the museum staff and teachers have the following objectives:

- to arouse the interest of visitors to our national values through the museum and its collections;

- Teach young people to treat museums with care and respect;
- Forming in young people a sense of belonging to the history and culture of our country, the introduction of activities on a common theme and pedagogical purpose on the basis of organized museum-pedagogical programs.

The concept of "museum pedagogy" in its essence means the implementation of the following functions:

Giving information - The museum primarily provides information to visitors in a particular area.

Giving education - The museum plays an important role in expanding the knowledge of visitors through the collection of materials.

In addition, during the communication process in the museum, visitors will have the opportunity to learn some skills and abilities in the field of museums. The museum is a place where you can learn more than other educational institutions.

Encouraging the development of creative abilities - the museum is a place that has a positive impact on the formation of the spiritual culture of the visitor in some areas, the discovery of his personal creative qualities. The museum has special conditions that encourage the individual to creative processes. Most importantly, it has an influential "inspiring" opportunity, reflecting the values, traditions and customs of the past.

Improving communicating - Adolescents are encouraged to communicate in a variety of museum-themed activities. The museum-information provided by the museum provides a convenient opportunity for communication, which leads to meaningful, interesting, informal personal communication. Conversations can take the form of meetings, seminars, quizzes and other events.

Museum-pedagogical programs have been introduced by museum staff in foreign museums. The programs consist mainly of interactive tours of museum halls for students, student audiences, and a variety of activities. In general, the content of the work organized and carried out in the field of education in the museum is very diverse. The main forms of this work are: traditional (excursions, lectures, public events), non-traditional (online classes, webinars, video conferences).

- We have developed the following scientific and methodological recommendations to improve the use of museum pedagogy in the education system of our country.

- Establishment of mechanisms for close cooperation between museums and educational institutions;

- Taking into account the pedagogical and psychological features of museum education when working with audiences of different ages;

- Development and implementation of innovative programs that integrate school and museum education in collaboration with museum staff and teachers of educational institutions ("School in a museum learning environment", "Museum pedagogy in school", "Museum and education", "Hello, museum!" ("Education through culture" and others.);

- Introduction of non-traditional forms and methods of teaching in museum pedagogy (online lessons, webinars, video conferences, film screenings, games, theatrical lessons and others.).

In conclusion, modern museum pedagogy is first and foremost about respecting the spirit of the ancestors of the past in the younger generation aimed at growing interest in the history of their homeland, developing creative abilities, the formation of museum culture in children and adolescents.

REFERENCES:

1. Ismailova J.Kh., Nishanova K.S., Mukhamedova M.S. Muzeyvajamiat. – T.: Chinor ENK, 2015. – 176 p.

2. Lichtwark A. *Obungen in der Betrachtung von Kunstwerken.* – Berlin: Verlag von Bruno Cassire, 1909. – 230p.
3. Stolyarov B.A. *The history of museum pedagogy, theory, practice-* M.: High. school., 2004 — 29-84p.
4. Ibragimovna, T. I. (2023). Preparing Future Educators for the Formation of Life Skills in Students. *World of Science: Journal on Modern Research Methodologies*, 2(3), 170-173.
5. Karimova, B. K., & Oripova, M. S. (2021). Formation of national pride based on hadiths in primary school children of houses of kindness. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 652-665.
6. Karimova, M. O., & Saidullaeva, A. R. (2020). Pedagogical basis of the use of universal and national values in the spiritual and moral education of children in the family. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(7), 8547-8555.
7. Marayimova, K. I. (2020). Museum excursions as an innovative approach in continuous education of students. *Solid State Technology*, 63(4), 5080-5085.
8. Marayimova, K. I. A SYSTEM FOR TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS IN TOURISM THROUGH MUSEUM PEDAGOGY Marayimova KI Email: Marayimova17148@scientifictext.ru.
9. Marayimova, K. I. Q. (2022). MUZEY PEDAGOGIKASI VOSITASIDA BO ‘LAJAK O ‘QITUVCHILARNI TURISTIK FAOLIYATGA YO ‘NALTIRISHNING MAZMUNI VA DIDAKTIK IMKONIYATLARI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(1), 17-26.
10. Muhammadjonovna, U. N., Makhmutovna, T. H., & Kurbonovich, M. U. (2020). IMPROVING THE MECHANISM OF INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A DEMOCRATIC AND LEGAL SOCIETY. *JCR*, 7(12), 3133-3139.

11. Mukhammedovna, U. N., & Oyturaxonovna, I. S. (2019). IMPROVING SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF YOUTH IN UZBEKISTAN AS THE DEMOCRACY AND DEVELOPMENT OF LEGAL SOCIETY. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(12)*.

12. Qizi, M. K. I. (2020). A system for training future teachers in tourism through museum pedagogy. *Проблемы современной науки и образования, (3 (148))*, 56-58.

13. Qizi, M. K. I. (2021). The role of museums in the development of tourism. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL, 11(2)*, 121-124.

14. SAIDKULOVICH, S. B., & UGLI, T. J. U. The Social Pedagogical Necessity of Developing Students' Aesthetic Culture in the Process of Globalization. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 8(1)*, 75-77.

15. Shermukhammadov, B. (2022). Creativity of a Teacher in an Innovative Educational Environment. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice, 22(12)*, 127.

16. Siddikov, B., & Djalalov, B. (2020, December). MODERNIZATION OF EDUCATION-THE FUTURE INNOVATIVE COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS AS A MAIN FACTOR OF FORMATION. In *Конференции*.

17. Siddiqov, B. S., & Mexmonaliyev, S. N. (2022). PEDAGOGIK AMALIYOTNING BO 'LAJAK O 'QITUVCHINING KASBIY TAYYORGARLIK FAOLIYATIDA TUTGAN O 'RNI. *Academic research in educational sciences, 3(1)*, 10-16.

18. Tuychiyeva, I., & Jo'Rayeva, S. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHDA KREDIT-MODUL TIZIMINING AHAMIYATI. *Science and innovation, 1(B7)*, 1349-1354.

19. Ugli, T. J. U. (2022). The role of aesthetic education in the preparation of future fine art teachers for professional activity. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 11(12), 60-64.

20. Urinova, N. M., & Abdullaeva, N. (2021). Opportunities to use project-based teaching technology in the development of students' research competence. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 2344-2348.

21. Ахмедов, Б. А. (2020). Сиддиков Бахтиёр Саидкулович, Джалалов Бахромжон Бегмурзаевич МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ-ОСНОВНОЙ ФАКТОР В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ. *Academy*, 9, 60.

22. Ахмедов, Б. А., Сиддиков, Б. С., & Джалалов, Б. Б. (2020). МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ-ОСНОВНОЙ ФАКТОР В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ. *Academy*, (9 (60)), 20-22.

23. Джалалов, Б. Б. (2018). РАЗВИТИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КАДРОВ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ КАК ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND EDUCATION* (pp. 53-55).

24. Джалалов, Б. Б. (2019). Важные аспекты формирования инновационных компетенций у будущих учителей. In *European research: innovation in science, education and technology* (pp. 43-44).

25. Джалалов, Б. Б. (2019). ВАЖНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ У БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ. In *EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY* (pp. 43-44).

26. Марайимова, К. И. (2022). ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ФОРМЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ЭКСКУРСИЙ В МУЗЕИ. *Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktika*, 2(6).

27. Сиддиқов, Б. С., & Джалалов, Б. Б. MODERNIZATION OF EDUCATION-THE FUTURE INNOVATIVE COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS AS A MAIN FACTOR OF FORMATION.

28. Уринова, Н. М. (2020). ПЕДАГОГИКА УНИВЕРСИТЕТЛАРИДА БЎЛАЖАК ЎҚИТУВЧИЛАРНИ МУЗЕЙ ПЕДАГОГИКАСИ ФАОЛИЯТИГА ТАЙЁРЛАШ БЎЙИЧА ХОРИЖИЙ ТАЖРИБАЛАР. *ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ*, (SI-2№ 7).

29. Шермухаммадов, Б. (2012). Использование различных методов, форм и средств в воспитании молодежи. *Актуальные проблемы современной науки*, (5), 80-83.